

Mortality from Nervous System Diseases in Italian Regions

It increased on average by 65.47% between 2004 and 2018

The Istat-Bes calculate mortality rates from nerve system diseases and psychic and behavioral disorders standardized within the 65-year age group and more. These data are available for 20 Italian regions from 2004 to 2018.

Ranking of the Italian regions for mortality rates of the diseases of the nervous system in 2018.

The Aosta Valley is in the first place for mortality rates of the diseases of the nervous system with a value of 54.9 units, followed by Sardinia with a value equal to 39.9 units and from the Veneto with an amount equal to 39.6 units. In the middle of the standings there are Emilia-Romagna with a value of 34.4, Tuscany with an amount of 32.3 units and Abruzzo with a value of 31.7 units. Calabria close the ranking with an amount equal to 25 units, followed by Campania with an amount of 24.9 units and by Molise with a value of 21.8 units. On average, the value of mortality from nerve system diseases was equal to a value of 33.04 units in 2019.

Ranking of the regions for percentage variation of mortality from the nerve system diseases between 2004 and 2018.

Trentino-Alto Adige is in the first place due to percentage variation of mortality from nervous system diseases with an amount of 159.86% equal to an amount of 22.70 units, followed by the Aosta Valley with an amount of 155.35% equal to an amount of 33.40 units and by Sardinia with an amount of 99.50% equal to an amount of 19.90 unit. In the middle of the standings there are Campania with an amount equal to 62.75% equal to an amount of 9.60 units, the Veneto with an amount of 62.30% equal to a value of 15.20 units, and Puglia with a value of 60.62% equal to a value of 11.70 units. Abruzzo close the ranking with a value of 36.64% equal to an amount of 8.50 units, Friuli-Venezia Giulia with an amount of 33.80% equal to an amount of 7.30 units and Liguria with a value equal to 31.34% equal to an amount of 8.40 units.

Italian macro-regions. Mortality from nerve disease has increased in all Italian macro-regions. In northern Italy, mortality from nerve disease is growing from an amount of 22.7 units up to a value of 36.1 units or equal to a value of 13.40 units equal to an amount of 59.03%. In Central Italy, the mortality from nerve disease has grown from an amount of 19.8 units up to a value of 31.1 units or equal to a value of 11.30 units equal to a value of 57.078%. In the South of Italy, mortality from nerve diseases grew from an amount of 17.8 units up to a value of 29.4 units equal to an amount of 11.60 units equal to a value of 65.17%. In Italy, the mortality from nerve disease has grown from an amount of 20.7 units up to a value of 33 units or equal to a variation of 12.30 units equal to a value of 59.42%.

Clusterization with K-means algorithm. Below is a clusterization with K-means algorithm optimized with the silhouette coefficient. The analysis shows the presence of two Clusters or:

- Cluster 1: Lazio, Basilicata, Campania, Molise, Calabria, Sicily, Friuli-Venezia Giulia, Puglia, Umbria, Trentino-Alto Adige, Tuscany;

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- Cluster 2: Veneto, Piedmont, Liguria, Sardinia, Abruzzo, Valle d'Aosta, Lombardy, Marche, Emilia-Romagna.

However, it should be considered that by analyzing the value of the Clusters median it appears that the value of the C1-Cluster 1 median is equal to a value of 28.9 while the value of the median of the 2-C2 cluster is equal to 36.1. It therefore follows that $C2 = 36.1 > C1 = 28.9$. From a geographical point of view, it is possible to note that mortality from nerve diseases tends to be more widespread in the center-north regions than the central-south regions. This difference is quite marked and could be traced, at least in part, to elements connected to individual and social life styles.

Machine Learning and Predictions. Eight different Machine Learning algorithms are compared for the prediction of the value of mortality from the nervous system diseases. The algorithms were optimized on the basis of their ability to maximize the R-Squared and to minimize the following statistical errors or: "Mean Absolute Error", "Means Squared Error", "Root Mean Squared Error". The algorithms were trained with 70% of the available data while the remaining 30% was used for the actual prediction. The following system of algorithms or:

- Ann-artificial neural network with a payoff value of 4;
- Gradient Boosted Tree with a payoff value of 8;
- Random Forest Regression with a payoff value of 12;
- Simple Regression Tree with a payoff value of 16;
- Tree Regression Ensemble with a payoff value of 20;
- PNN-Probabilistic Neural Network with a payoff value of 24;
- Polynomial Regression with a payoff value of 28;
- Linear Regression with a payoff value of 32.

Below by applying the Ann-Artificial Neural Network algorithm, the predictions for the regions that are indicated below are carried out or:

- Lombardy with a diminutive variation from an amount of 0.432 up to a value of 0.345 or equal to an amount of -0.087 units equal to a value of -20.13%;
- Trentino Alto Adige with a variation from an amount of 0.456 units up to a value of 0.348 units or equal to an amount of -0.108 units equal to a value of -23.684%;
- Friuli Venezia Giulia with a diminutive variation from an amount of 0.215 up to a value of 0.152 units or equal to a variation of -0.063 units equal to a value of -29.30%;
- Campania with an increased variation from an amount of 0.094 units up to a value of 0.125 units or equal to a variation of 0.031 units equal to a value of 32.97%;
- Calabria with an increased variation from an amount of 0.097 units up to a value of 0.125 units or equal to a variation of 0.028 units equal to an amount of 28.86%;
- Sicily with an increased variation from an amount of 0.263 units up to a value of 0.277 units or equal to a variation of 0.014 units equal to a value of 5.323%.

Overall, on average, the value of mortality from nerve diseases is required in decrease from an amount equal to 0.26 up to a value of 0.22 units or equal to a value of -0.031 units equal to a value of -11.88%

Conclusions. The data show an increasing trend of mortality from nerve disease after 65 years. This trend is common to all Italian regions. In the regions of the Center-North there is more mortality from nerve diseases than the center-south. This phenomenon is particularly worrying and could indicate an inability of the health system to deal with the needs of the population. Furthermore, it must be considered that in the general phenomenon of aging of the population the percentage of mortality from the nervous system diseases could grow further. The result is the need to create changes in local

health systems to make sure that there is greater assistance and care for patients with the diseases of the nervous system.

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	2004	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018
Piemonte	22	25,2	25	25,7	30,7	32,2	30,9	31,5	33,3	31,9	30,9	36,4	34,1	36,9	35,9
Valle d'Aosta/Vallée d'Aoste	21,5	23,4	29,2	36,9	40,4	40	37,8	40,5	41,7	43,9	31,9	48,5	46,9	60,5	54,9
Liguria	26,8	27,2	31,2	29,4	34,6	35,4	33,9	34,9	34,8	32,9	31,5	35,1	33,1	34,1	35,2
Lombardia	21,5	24,2	23,6	25,2	31,2	31	30,4	30,6	31,7	29,9	29,4	33,9	33,2	35,5	36,1
Trentino-Alto Adige/Südtirol	14,2	19,7	20,5	22	24	23,3	27,1	29,3	30,2	30	30,2	30,6	34,7	37	36,9
Veneto	24,4	25	26,1	26,6	32,9	33,8	33,3	33,4	34,2	33,4	32,6	36,2	38,7	39,8	39,6
Friuli-Venezia Giulia	21,6	20,9	22,6	23,9	27,6	28	27	28,8	27,3	27,9	25	28,7	28,8	31,5	28,9
Emilia-Romagna	23,6	24,7	25,2	25,8	31,2	30,4	29,2	30	29,9	28,5	27,8	31,7	32,7	34,2	34,4
Toscana	20,5	23,7	23,5	23,9	28,9	28,8	27,3	29,1	28,5	27,6	27,2	31,8	30,6	33,6	32,3
Umbria	20,7	22,4	22	24,4	27,7	27,9	26,9	26,8	29,8	24,6	25,6	31,7	32,4	34,2	29,4
Marche	20,6	22,4	22,4	25,1	28	29,1	31,3	29,8	32	30,2	30,5	35,2	33,3	40,2	36,5
Lazio	18,6	19,6	19,4	20,9	24,9	25,1	25,2	24,2	26,5	22,9	23	27,4	26,7	30,7	28,7
Abruzzo	23,2	25,9	25,9	28,1	32,5	32	31,7	30,5	33,7	30,5	29,2	34,8	31,8	35,1	31,7
Molise	15,2	18,9	21	21,1	20	26,2	23,8	21,7	24,9	22,7	21,7	27,5	24,8	26,4	21,8
Campania	15,3	17,9	16,6	18,8	20,3	21,6	21,1	22,7	22,3	22,2	22,1	25,7	23,2	27,3	24,9
Puglia	19,3	21,6	22,9	25,4	27,4	27,3	27,2	27,6	29,1	27,7	27,7	32	29	32,5	31
Basilicata	17,6	17,8	19,2	18,8	24,2	22,4	22,1	24,5	21,4	21,9	22,9	26,7	26	29,4	27,3
Calabria	15,3	17,2	15,9	19	20,8	20,9	20,5	20,3	23,8	21	22	24,7	22,2	25,7	25
Sicilia	17,5	19,9	20,4	21,5	25,7	27,2	25,1	26,7	29,1	26,5	26,9	29,8	27,9	33	30,5
Sardegna	20	21,7	22,8	22,7	32,1	33,2	29,9	31,7	35,6	32,5	33,9	36,4	37,1	42,6	39,9

Clusterization. C2>C1

